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HIPPARCOS reductions for multiple stars, XVIIIb
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This is the sequel report to NDAC/LO/145 about the '1.5-year' DS-reductions, giving some statistical results from the first runs of STDDBL and SEEKDBL, and also an empirical calibration of the IFOV-profile.

1. Results for known doubles

The Case History Files for 10500 known doubles have been derived, and solutions have been attempted for 10487 of them. The STDDBL program has been run a number of times (with different parameter selections) and for the majority of systems, it is possible to give either a double-star or an (equally good) single-star solution. Depending on the acceptance criteria used, there will however also be a 'middle zone' with poor or missing solutions. These criteria will be refined, but in a first round of solutions, a 'good' solution does not violate any of the following rules:

1. The normalized χ^2 -fit to the observations is below 4.5 on a scale where the mean is about 1.5.
2. The Δm_{eff} -parameter has to be below 4.0
3. The calculated absolute and relative position mean errors (mas) have to obey

$$\begin{aligned} \lg \sigma_{\text{abs}} &< \max(1.0, 1.0 + 0.25(H_p - 7)) \\ \lg \sigma_{\text{rel}} &< \max(0.5, 0.5 + 0.15(H_p - 7)) + 0.4 \max(2, \Delta m) \end{aligned}$$

With these criteria, a first round of solutions gave 6851 'OK doubles', 839 double star solutions violating some criterion, 590 'problem cases' without either a double or a single-star solution, and finally 1884 systems where only a single-star solution is obtained or where a double star solution is not significantly better. (For some reason, this adds up to only 10164 systems, but a few hundred solutions more or less is typical when some solution-parameter is changed, and I do not think a more detailed accounting is necessary at this stage). The accepted solutions are shown in Fig. 1 in a standard $\lg \rho - \Delta m$ diagram. The lack of systems at upper left is a real observational selection effect, but at upper right the systems with $\Delta m > 3$ were not flagged as double in the Input Catalogue. As expected, most of the 'effective single' solutions are obtained for systems with $\Delta m_{\text{eff}}(IC) > 4$.

Fig. 1. The preliminarily accepted STDDBL-solutions (for known doubles) in a $\lg \rho - \Delta m$ diagram. Lines of constant Δm_{eff} (2,3,4) are also indicated.

Excluding the systems with separation $\rho < 0.3$, one may plot the relation between the (formal) relative position error and Δm as shown at left in Fig. 2. This relation (with a slope similar to that found in simulations, cf. Fig 13.6, p. 233 in ESA SP-1111, III) gives the typical accuracy for the relative double-star positions. To the right is given the very similar plot for the mean errors of the magnitude differences (Δm) between the components.

Fig. 2. Formal mean errors in the relative positions (left diagram) or in the Δm :s (right diagram) as a function of Δm_{eff} for 5490 STDDBL solutions with $H_p(pr) < 10$.

Qualitatively similar plots are obtained for separations < 0.3 arcsec with Δm_{eff} on the abscissa, but with somewhat different slopes and intercepts. (This shows that the definition of Δm_{eff} is due for a revision, but so far the old one, introduced already in 1986, is kept unchanged). For separations smaller than the diffraction resolution for a 29 cm telescope, the error-increase is mostly due to an increased correlation between the separations and the magnitude differences. A smaller

separation and a smaller magnitude difference may mimic fairly well a larger separation and a fainter companion. From the solution covariance-matrices one may derive these correlations explicitly, as shown in Fig. 3. (Some 1900 SEEKDBL solutions are included at separations below 1 arcsec). Somewhat unexpectedly, the increase starts already at about 0.50 arcsec ($1.2\lambda/D=0.43$ arcsec at 5000 Å).

Fig. 3. Correlation between the separation and the magnitude difference as a function of separation for 6596 STDDBL and SEEKDBL solutions.

The 'absolute' parallax mean errors are even more interesting. In Fig 4 the insignificant variations with Δm_{eff} or separation are shown (note, however the slight increase for 2-pointing doubles at about 20 arcsec separation). In the upper part of Fig 5 are shown the more obvious variations with magnitude or ecliptic latitude. These plots may be compared with corresponding ones for single stars in the lower part of the figure. Although an increased scatter for the doubles is immediately apparent, the main relations are very similar, and good parallaxes may certainly be obtained for most of the doubles also.

Fig 4. The formal parallax error as a function of Δm_{eff} or $\lg$ separation for 6866 STDDBL solutions.

Fig. 5. The formal parallax error as a function of H_p -magnitude or ecliptic latitude for the 6866 STDDBL solutions above (upper panels) or 6624 SEEKDBL single-star solutions (lower panels).

2. Results for new doubles

CHF:s were generated for 10647 suspected non-singles, and solutions have been attempted for 10625 of these. As reported in NDAC/LO/145, I have also used a sample of 15832 'bona-fide singles', and to study the appearance of spurious solutions, these were run through SEEKDBL with the same parameters as the 'suspect' objects. (In particular, the search-mesh includes separations up to 2.5 arcsec). Independent of any parameter-choices, there is a strong (and so far unexplained) tendency for spurious solutions at certain specific separations close to one or two slit-periods.

Fig 6 shows the 'suspect' solutions (after the acceptance-criteria above for the known doubles have been applied), and it is at once apparent that the solutions with separations above 1 arcsec and magnitude-differences above 2 are *not* trustworthy. Very interestingly, 57 of the (merely) 64 double-star solutions obtained for the 'bona-fide singles' also fall in this area! After removing the 'bad' area of Fig 6, the remaining 2620 'new' objects beautifully complement Fig 1 above.

Fig. 6. A priori distribution of the SEEKDBL-solutions for 'suspected non-singles' in a $\lg \rho - \Delta m$ -diagram. The enclosed area at upper right is deleted due to problems with spurious solutions.

As in STDDBL, there are also rather many systems where neither a single-star nor a double-star solutions fits the observations. In the run giving 2620 'OK' doubles, 1078 objects fall in this category. These 'problem'-cases seem in many cases related to photometric variability, and methods will have to be devised for a proper treatment of duplicity plus variability. (To make up the total number of CHF:s, single-star solutions seem to fit the observations for 5158 objects, while 1769 original double-star solutions are excluded for any of the reasons listed above).

3. The effective IFOV-profile

For the 2-pointing doubles (with separations 10-35") a parameter x_p is solved for, checking implicitly the adopted IFOV-profile. The 'effective' profile, including the spread due to IDT piloting and catalogue errors, is simply

$$f_{\text{eff}}(r) = f_{\text{nom}}(rx_p)$$

at the r corresponding to the actual separation. Taking means over different separation-intervals, the nominal profile has been successively refined in the important interval $10 < r < 35$ arcsec. The profile finally adopted is a spline function through the knots listed in Table 1. The 'mean errors' given are calculated from the mean errors in x_p where available. Fig. 7 shows the profile (in magnitude units) together with the early observations by Phil Davies (Hipparcos status report 4, nov 1989). Ideally, the present curve should lie above the measured points (except at small separations!), being the convolution of the true profile with a total pointing uncertainty some 2-3 arcsec. The measures for separations above 25 arcsec seem thus too high, but at such a large attenuation, this is probably not unreasonable.

Table 1. The adopted effective IFOV-profile $f_{\text{eff}}(r)$. Mean errors are estimated from the STDDBL solutions.

r [arcs]	$f_{\text{eff}}(r)$	m.e.	r [arcs]	$f_{\text{eff}}(r)$	m.e.
0.	0.9964		24.	0.0752	0.0025
3.	0.9948		28.	0.0107	0.0007
6.	0.9837		32.	0.0022	0.0001
9.	0.9489	0.0016	36.	0.0015	
12.	0.8553	0.0055	40.	0.0013	
15.	0.6780	0.0054	44.	0.0012	
18.	0.4494	0.0042	48.	0.0010	
21.	0.2291	0.0041			

Fig 7. The adopted effective IFOV-profile with attenuation in magnitudes. Over the interval 10-34 arcsec, the error derived from STDDBL solutions is below 0.05 magnitudes.

4. Conclusions

The main conclusion from the above is that the DS reductions for 'simple' (known or unknown) doubles are now well in hand. There are fairly large numbers of systems that do *not* get either a single or a double solution, and new methods will have to be devised for them. Allowance must be made for photometric variability of the components, instead of the present assumption of constancy inherent in a global solution. Solution programs for more than two components must be finalized, as well as methods to treat systems with non-linear motions.